

Post- Operative Analgesic Effect of Intra- Peritoneal 0.5% Ropivacaine With and Without Tramadol in Laparoscopic Abdominal Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: Managing postoperative pain is essential in laparoscopic abdominal surgeries to enhance recovery, minimize complications, and reduce hospital stays. Intraperitoneal administration of local anesthetics like ropivacaine has become a popular approach to managing visceral and somatic pain post-surgery. Recent studies suggest that combining local anesthetics with opioids like tramadol can further improve pain relief, although it might be linked to adverse symptoms including nausea.

Aim: To assess the intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine's postoperative analgesic efficacy in laparoscopic abdominal procedures in terms of pain scores, the need for rescue analgesia, and side effect profiles, both with and without tramadol.

Methods: A randomised controlled trial with double blinding was carried out on 100 patients receiving laparoscopic abdominal surgery in a prospective manner. Patients were randomly assigned to Group A (15 ml of 0.5% ropivacaine with 15 ml saline) or Group B (4 ml tramadol, 15 ml of 0.5% ropivacaine, and 11 ml saline). At several times after surgery, pain was assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). The duration of the first rescue analgesia, the total amount of analgesics used, and any side effects were noted. An analysis using statistics was done.

Results: Group B (ropivacaine + tramadol) had significantly lower VAS pain scores compared to Group A (ropivacaine alone) at most time intervals, particularly during the first 12 hours post-surgery ($p < 0.05$). Group B also required significantly less rescue analgesia and had lower total morphine consumption within 24 hours ($p < 0.001$). While nausea was more common in Group B (12% vs 2% in Group A, $p = 0.045$), no other significant adverse effects were observed.

Conclusion: Better pain management is achieved in the early postoperative phase when intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine plus tramadol is used instead of ropivacaine alone. Although this combination is linked to a higher rate of nausea, it is a useful strategy for managing pain after laparoscopic procedures since it lowers the requirement for rescue analgesia and the overall amount of opioids used.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to optimize tramadol dosing to balance effective pain relief with minimal side effects. This combination therapy could be integrated into enhanced recovery protocols to improve patient outcomes post-laparoscopic surgery.

Keywords: Postoperative pain, Laparoscopic surgery, Ropivacaine, Tramadol, Intraperitoneal analgesia.

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Introduction

Recovery from surgery depends on effective postoperative pain treatment particularly in laparoscopic abdominal surgeries, which, while minimally invasive, still cause significant postoperative pain. Uncontrolled pain can impede recovery, prolong hospital stays, and increase the risk of complications, including respiratory issues, delayed wound healing, and even chronic pain

syndromes [1]. Postoperative pain in laparoscopic surgeries often includes a combination of somatic, visceral, and referred pain, particularly from pneumoperitoneum-related irritation of the phrenic nerve, which manifests as shoulder pain [2]. Therefore, optimizing pain control strategies is essential for enhancing patient outcomes and accelerating recovery.

Intraperitoneal local anesthetic administration has gained popularity for postoperative pain relief in laparoscopic surgeries due to its direct action on visceral nociceptors. Ropivacaine, an amide local anesthetic, is commonly used because of its longer duration of action and lower systemic toxicity compared to other agents like bupivacaine [3]. The blocking of sodium channels in nerve cells is its mechanism of action, which stops pain signals from being sent [4]. Despite the efficacy of ropivacaine in reducing postoperative pain, its effects can be enhanced when combined with adjuvant drugs.

Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake are inhibited by Tramadol, a centrally acting opioid analgesic that acts weakly on μ -opioid receptors has emerged as a valuable adjunct to local anesthetics. When combined with ropivacaine, tramadol can potentiate the analgesic effect through both peripheral and central mechanisms [5]. Recent studies suggest that the addition of tramadol to local anesthetics significantly improves postoperative pain control, delays the need for rescue analgesia, and reduces overall opioid consumption [6]. However, higher doses of tramadol are often associated with adverse effects like nausea, vomiting, and sedation, which necessitate careful dosing [7]. The study aimed to assess the intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine's postoperative analgesic efficacy in laparoscopic abdominal procedures in terms of pain scores, the need for rescue analgesia, and side effect profiles, both with and without tramadol.

Methodology

Study Design: This trial was randomised, controlled, double-blinded, and prospective.

Study Setting: With institutional ethics committee approval, the study was carried out in a hospital setting. Participants in the study included those having laparoscopic abdominal procedures.

Participants: 100 patients categorised as having ASA-PS grades I and II and scheduled for laparoscopic abdominal surgery, were included in the study. The patients ranged in age from 18 to 60.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals with ages ranging from 18 to 60.
- Grade I and II ASA-PS patients.
- Individuals slated for elective laparoscopic abdominal procedures.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with ASA-PS grade III or higher.
- Individuals with impaired liver or renal function.

- History of arrhythmias, hypersensitivity to study drugs, or seizures.
- Patients undergoing laparoscopic hernia repair.

Bias: Patients were randomly assigned to one of two groups using sealed opaque envelopes holding computer-generated assignments in order to reduce bias. The study was double-blinded; neither the patients nor the clinicians administering the postoperative care knew the group assignments.

Data Collection: Various parameters were gathered, such as the time to initial rescue analgesia, the total analgesic dose, adverse events associated to the medicine, and postoperative pain levels using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). Pain scores were assessed periodically, at ½ hour, 1 hour, 2 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, 12 hours, and 24 hours after surgery, haemodynamic data were also recorded.

Procedure: Patients were arbitrarily divided into two groups: Fifty millilitres of 0.5% ropivacaine were combined with fifteen millilitres of saline in Group A. Group B received 200 mg of tramadol, 15 millilitres of 0.5% ropivacaine, and 11 millilitres of saline. The prescribed medication combination was sprayed intraperitoneally via three laparoscopic ports while the patients were in the Trendelenburg position before the port removal. VAS was used to quantify pain after surgery at predetermined intervals. Morphine was given to patients as rescue analgesia if their VAS score was ≥ 3 .

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was employed for data analysis. The frequency distribution was calculated using descriptive statistics. While the Mann-Whitney U test examined the amount of analgesic used overall, the duration to rescue analgesia, and the VAS scores between groups, chi-square tests evaluated connections between categorical variables. VAS score changes over time.

Results

In this randomized controlled trial, 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic abdominal surgeries were assigned to two groups of 50: Group B received tramadol with intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine, while Group A did not. Hemodynamic factors, postoperative pain scores, rescue analgesia, side effects, and baseline characteristics were assessed. Both groups were comparable in age, gender, ASA status, and weight, with no significant correlations. The average age was approximately 44 years in Group A and 42 years in Group B.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Age (years)	44.12 ± 13.19	41.56 ± 12.82	0.327
Gender (Male/Female)	11/39	9/41	0.617
ASA-PS Grade (I/II)	58% / 42%	64% / 36%	0.539
Weight (kg)	63.58 ± 10.45	63.52 ± 11.06	0.927

Table 2: Baseline Hemodynamic Variables (At the time of drug instillation)

Variable	Group A (Mean ± SD)	Group B (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Heart Rate (beats/min)	80.78 ± 8.29	82.02 ± 9.19	0.480
Systolic BP (mmHg)	121.76 ± 14.13	124.72 ± 16.02	0.330
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	76.40 ± 7.78	78.36 ± 8.42	0.230
Oxygen Saturation (%)	98.60 ± 0.83	98.92 ± 0.99	0.083

(VAS) was used to determine postoperative pain at predetermined intervals following surgery. In comparison to Group A, Group B's pain scores were significantly reduced at most time intervals after receiving 0.5% ropivacaine together with tramadol.

Table 3: Comparison of Mean VAS Scores between Group A & Group B

Time Interval	Group A (Mean ± SD)	Group B (Mean ± SD)	p-value
30 minutes	2.74 ± 0.90	2.30 ± 0.58	0.005**
1 hour	3.28 ± 1.03	2.36 ± 0.94	<0.01**
2 hours	2.76 ± 0.89	2.16 ± 0.82	0.001**
4 hours	2.20 ± 0.64	1.84 ± 0.79	0.014**
6 hours	1.88 ± 0.72	1.76 ± 0.59	0.364
12 hours	1.62 ± 0.53	1.40 ± 0.49	0.034**
24 hours	1.44 ± 0.50	1.36 ± 0.48	0.419

Note: p-value < 0.05 is considered statistically significant (**).

Time to Rescue Analgesia: Comparatively to patients in Group A, those in Group B (ropivacaine + tramadol) experienced a delayed start of pain that required rescue analgesia. Although there was not a statistically significant distinction between Group A and Group B (p = 0.142), the mean time to first rescue analgesia was 60.00 ± 38.21 minutes for Group A and 86.43 ± 51.94 minutes for Group B.

Total Analgesic Consumption: Group B required significantly less rescue analgesia (morphine) compared to Group A. The total morphine

consumption within 24 hours was 2.76 ± 3.20 mg in Group A, while it was only 0.42 ± 1.05 mg in Group B, it had statistical value (p < 0.001).

Adverse Effects: Adverse effects following surgery were closely observed in both groups. With a p-value of 0.045, Group B (12%) had a substantially higher frequency of nausea than Group A (2%). But there were no other noteworthy side effects, such drowsiness or vomiting, that were noticed in either group.

Table 4: Incidence of Adverse Effects

Adverse Effect	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Nausea	1 (2%)	6 (12%)	0.045**
Vomiting	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	0.564
Sedation	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0.314

p-value < 0.05 is considered statistically significant (**).

Summary of Findings:

- Compared to Group A (ropivacaine alone), Group B (ropivacaine with tramadol) exhibited noticeably reduced pain scores at the majority of time intervals.
- Group B required significantly less rescue analgesia and had a lower total analgesic consumption within 24 hours postoperatively.

- Although Group B experienced a higher incidence of postoperative nausea, it was not associated with other severe adverse effects.

Discussion

The results suggest that the combination of intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine with tramadol offers superior postoperative pain control compared to ropivacaine alone in laparoscopic abdominal surgeries. However, this combination could be

linked to an increased frequency of minor side effects like nausea. The primary finding is that the combination of ropivacaine and tramadol (Group B) offers superior pain relief compared to ropivacaine alone (Group A) over the first 24 hours post-surgery.

Group B continuously reported reduced VAS pain scores at most time intervals in terms of postoperative pain scores. Following surgery, Group B experienced much less pain at 30 minutes, 1 hour, 2 hours, and 4 hours than Group A. By 12 hours, this trend persisted, further demonstrating that the combination of ropivacaine and tramadol provides longer-lasting analgesia. Nevertheless, a day later, there was no longer a statistically significant variance between the groups, suggesting that tramadol's effects might decrease down in the last stages of recovery. This indicates that adding tramadol to ropivacaine significantly enhances early postoperative pain management.

Rescue analgesia was also markedly affected by the combination therapy. In comparison to patients in Group A, patients in Group B took longer to receive rescue analgesia; however, this difference was not statistically noteworthy. However, Group B required significantly less total morphine over within the initial day following surgery, underscoring the effectiveness of the ropivacaine-tramadol combination in reducing the need for opioid-based rescue analgesia. Notably, 86% of patients in Group B did not require rescue analgesia compared to only 46% in Group A, highlighting the superior efficacy of the combination treatment.

Hemodynamic parameters between the two groups showed some differences as well. Systolic blood pressure was much lower in Group B at the drug's onset, two hours, and four hours administration, indicating more effective pain relief, as untreated pain often leads to elevated blood pressure. Additionally, oxygen saturation was lower in Group B at the 12-hour mark, which might be attributable to the sedative effects of tramadol. However, the decrease in oxygen saturation did not fall below clinically concerning levels.

In terms of **adverse effects**, there was a greater incidence of nausea when tramadol and ropivacaine were combined. Group B had a significantly greater number of patients experiencing postoperative nausea (12%) compared to Group A (2%). This side effect may be attributed to tramadol's interaction with opioid receptors in chemoreceptor trigger zone, which is known to trigger nausea at higher doses. Despite this, no other significant adverse effects, such as vomiting or sedation, were observed between the groups, indicating that tramadol was well-tolerated overall.

Numerous studies have validated the use of local anaesthetics and opioids to enhance postoperative

pain relief in laparoscopic surgeries. This study aligns with findings from Khurana et al. (2016), who observed lower systolic blood pressure and better pain control with intraperitoneal bupivacaine and buprenorphine compared to bupivacaine alone [8]. Similarly, Modir et al. (2021) found no significant correlation in oxygen saturation between ropivacaine and ropivacaine-opioid combinations, echoing our findings that tramadol-induced sedation did not significantly affect oxygen levels [9].

Postoperative pain management studies have consistently shown that combining local anesthetics with opioids results in lower pain scores. Karaman et al. (2012) demonstrated reduced pain scores with a ropivacaine-pethidine combination compared to ropivacaine alone [10]. Likewise, Shukla et al. (2015) and Kumari et al. (2020) reported that adding tramadol to ropivacaine significantly less pain and the requirement for analgesic rescue medication [11, 12].

Rescue analgesia requirements were also notably decreased in the combination groups across multiple studies. Raipuria et al. (2023) discovered that the inclusion of tramadol to ropivacaine significantly delayed the reduction in the overall amount of morphine consumed and the duration of the first rescue analgesic when compared to ropivacaine alone [13]. This reduction in opioid consumption is a critical factor in minimizing postoperative side effects and accelerating recovery.

However, the higher incidence of nausea in the tramadol groups has been a common finding. Our study found a similar increase in postoperative nausea, as did Raipuria et al. (2023), though this effect did not significantly alter the overall patient outcomes.

These findings support the growing evidence that intraperitoneal administration of local anesthetics, when combined with opioids like tramadol, provides enhanced pain relief, saves the need for opioid rescue analgesia and facilitates better healing for patients in laparoscopic surgeries.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that combining intraperitoneal 0.5% ropivacaine with tramadol provides better postoperative pain relief than ropivacaine alone in laparoscopic abdominal surgeries. Patients receiving the combination therapy had lower levels of pain, decreased usage of opioids, and postponed requirement for rescue analgesia. Although tramadol increased the incidence of nausea, its overall benefits in pain management make it a valuable option. This combination offers an effective and well-tolerated approach for enhancing recovery and reducing

opioid dependence post-surgery. Further research could refine dosing to minimize side effects.

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